

Introduction

The eurasian griffon vulture (*Gyps fulvus*) is one of the raptor species negatively affected the most by wind energy development. However it's still not clear what makes a wind turbine dangerous for griffons. In the study area, in the Strait of Gibraltar (Cádiz, Spain) we have undergone 123 hours of simultaneous direct observations at 10 dangerous and 10 safe wind turbines. The turbines have been surveyed from the 8th of October to the 23rd of November. Sampling time encompassed the migration time of the species when 4000-5000 griffons gather in the study area before crossing the Strait. The number of griffons and their behaviour in proximity of the turbines were recorded for each turbine.

Materials & methods

In order to test for differences in vulture behaviour between dangerous and safe turbines ten wind turbines that never killed a griffon and ten with the highest collision rate (n.griffons killed/months of career) were selected. The day was divided in three parts: morning (09:00-11:30), noon (11:31-14:30) and afternoon (14:31-17:30). Flying griffons and dangerous interactions with turbines were recorded for each turbine, altogether with their type of fight (fapped or soared), wind direction and wind intensity on the Beaufort's scale. Recorded griffons were also ranked in classes of distance from the wind turbines: 0-10m, 10-50m, 50-100m, 100-200m, 200-400m, >400m.

Results

Griffons recorded: randomized Wilcoxon's test showed significant differences in the total number of griffons observed and in the total number of dangerous interactions between the two groups of turbines. This is especially true for noon and afternoon, while non significant difference has been found in the morning, probably due to the daily activity pattern of the species. At dangerous turbines there was a positive and significant correlation between the number of griffons observed and the mortality rate (Spearman's rho = 0.72, p<0.01); moreover there was a positive and significant correlation between the number of dangerous interactions and the mortality rate (Spearman's rho = 0.66, p<0.01). In both safe (Spearman's rho = 0.89, p<0.01) and dangerous turbines (Spearman's rho = 0.89, p<0.01) the number of recorded griffons was strongly correlated with the number of dangerous interactions.

Flight behaviour: chi-square test for independence revealed significant differences in the distance of flying griffons from the turbines, in the two groups. Fisher's independence test for contingency tables highlighted significant differences in the proportions of griffons that flew at less than 100m, between dangerous and safe turbines. Mantel-Haenszel's test revealed significant differences in the proportion of griffons that adopted fapped flight for stronger eastern winds (Levante) and weaker western winds (Ponente) in a 100 m buffer around the turbines.

Discussion and conclusion

Our results seem to point out clear differences between dangerous and safe turbines. Dangerous wind turbines seem to have a higher number of griffons frequenting their surroundings, thereby a higher number of dangerous interactions between vultures and rotating blades. Moreover they seem to have a greater proportion of birds flying close to them. Vulture behaviour in proximity of the turbines is influenced by the type of wind but this relationship is still not clear. However the strong correlation between recorded birds, dangerous interactions and mortality rate of turbines suggests that surveys could be an useful management tool in wind-turbines impact assessment and mitigation measures allocation.

Distance	Safe turbines	Dangerous turbines
< 100 m from turbines	147	1244
> 100m from turbines	587	1863
Fisher's test for independence	odds-ratio 0.37	P p < 0.01

		Safe turbines	Dangerous turbines	Wilcoxon's test	
				Z	P
Griffons recorded (mean)	Total	73.8	324.7	2.798	p < 0.01
	Morning	2.7	22	n.s	n.s
	Noon	33.8	199.4	2.49	p < 0.05
	Afternoon	37.30	103.3	2.19	p < 0.05
Dangerous interactions (mean)	Total	1.2	12.6	2.69	p < 0.05
	Morning	0	1.3	n.s	n.s
	Noon	0.7	1.8	n.s	n.s
	Afternoon	0.5	9.9	2.55	p < 0.01

	Wind Direction	Safe turbines	
		East	West
Type of flight	Soared	14	32
	Flapped	22	58
Dangerous turbines			
Type of flight	Soared	72	118
	Flapped	216	813
Mantel-Haenszel test for independence			
2		P	
22.37		p < 0.01	